

Special Relativity, Rest Frame and Clock and Non-Clock Based Momentum Measurement

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Momentum of a particle with rest mass m_0 is $m_0 v$ (where v is velocity) nonrelativistically. This suggests that if one calculates p by measuring v , a clock is needed. On the other hand, one may measure p using an impulse and no clock is needed. It seems that one may choose one approach or the other with the same probability. This follows, however, because there is a rest mass implying a rest frame.

In the 1800s, Maxwell wrote electromagnetic equations for the electric and magnetic fields which make use of charges and currents. He considered the case with charges and currents set equal to zero. We suggest that if charges and currents are removed, there is no longer the sense of a rest frame. There is, however, still the sense of energy in the electric and magnetic fields and the sense of momentum density given by the Poynting expression $1/u_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$. We argue that if there is no special rest frame, then all frames are on the same footing and that there should be one velocity value namely c . If this were not the case, one could arrange velocity values from lowest to highest with the lowest pointing to a special frame. Furthermore, since there is no rest frame there is no energy \times velocity for momentum and no clock is needed to measure momentum. It should only be measured through an impulse hit.

From nonrelativistic mechanics, E has the units of $p \times$ speed. In the case of no rest reference frame, the only speed in the picture is c and so one may propose $E = |p|c$, or $E^2 = p^2 c^2$. Here E is a kinetic type of energy because it only exists if there is motion, i.e. p . Nonrelativistically, however, $KE = p^2/2m_0$ which is very different in form even though p may be measured as an impulse for both cases. This begs the question: Why are the energy forms so different if both are only due to motion? A key difference in the energy forms is the appearance of m_0 in KE . Why should this be necessary if KE is strictly kinetic energy and $E = pc$? Furthermore, the notion of KE arises from the idea of work done on a mass. A rest mass has inertia and work must be done to get it to move and so it seems one cannot rule out the idea of the rest mass changing in a certain sense. In other words, just as p may be measured without using a clock, rest mass is linked with a clock because time goes by and one might think of a total energy when it moves, not just a kinetic one. As a result, m_0 and $p=0$ may transform into E , p where E is now a full energy. In the case of $m_0=0$, one should obtain $E^2 = p^2 c^2$ so we suggest: $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$. This equation accounts for p and $-p$, but is also of the form of a kind of modulus of a vector which transforms E and p together which applies to the no rest frame case and should also hold for the rest frame one for consistency.

We suggest that the association of p with a measurement not requiring a clock and the association of rest mass and energy as being linked with a clock maps into the quantum mechanical view of $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ for which there is a time resolution of \hbar/E and a spatial one of \hbar/p .

Maxwell's Equations

Maxwell wrote differential equations for electric E and magnetic B fields which involve charges and currents. If one has a single charge, one may go into its rest frame and so there is a special frame. If, however, one considers these equations with all charge sources and currents set to zero, as Maxwell did, then there is no preferred rest frame anymore, we suggest.

There is, however, still the notion of energy and momentum in the fields given by $\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2\mu_0} B \cdot B$ and $\frac{1}{\mu_0} E \times B$. (These are densities.)

In order to have momentum, there must be motion, implying a speed. We argue that if there is no special rest frame, this speed should be the same for any different moving frame, i.e. c because otherwise the speed would characterize the frame. In particular, if there may speeds, one could arrange them from lowest to highest and the lowest would point to a frame closest to a rest frame. This is a contradiction because there is no rest frame.

Nonrelativistically, $p = m_0 v$ where m_0 is rest mass and v speed. This equation cannot hold for the case of no rest frame, yet p still exists. For $p = m_0 v$ one may use a clock to measure v , but in both this case and the no rest frame case, one may also measure p using impulse hits which do not require a clock. One may simply measure the damage caused by a photon with p hitting a target. Given that one has a case for which one may only use impulse hits to measure p , i.e. the no rest frame (photon case), it seems that the non-clock measurement approach is a more general one when it comes to p . If one only had $p = m_0 v$, one has a 50-50% choice to either measure v or impulse. We suggest that this is an important idea because it means that p measurement may occur with no clocks present. This, we argue, is what one does when one uses time-independent quantum mechanics.

If E and p are present for the non rest mass case and there is only one speed c , then:

$$E = |p|c \text{ or } E^2 = p^2 c^2 \quad ((1))$$

If $x'/t' = c$ for all frames then: $x' - ct' = 0$ for all frames moving with different constant values.

Given that $E = |p|c$, one has: $-Et + px = 0$, i.e. this is an invariant for all frames. (Note, even though there is no rest frame for E , B , the ruler and clock have a rest frame and this frame then may be boosted (i.e. be seen to move with a velocity v .)

The Rest Mass Case

((1)) describes a kinetic energy E linked to p . In nonrelativistic mechanics, however,

$$KE = p^2 / 2m_0 \quad ((2))$$

In both cases, p has the same physical meaning when measured by an impulse hit which does not require a clock, yet the energy dependence on p is very different. Furthermore, m_0 appears in ((2)). If one were to set $m_0 = 0$, but still insist on KE and p existing, one does not obtain ((1)). ((1)) suggests that for consistency there should be a full E with p such that:

$$EE = ppcc + m_0 \text{ function}(m_0, p, E) \quad ((3))$$

If $m_0=0$, then $EE = ppcc$. $EE = ppcc$ for the photon, however, suggests that E and p are on the same footing and this should also be the case for ((3)). In other words, $m_0, p=0$ should still have an E value and this should transform to E', p' when viewed from a frame moving with constant v . This then seems to suggest that m_0 is proportional to E in the rest frame so that $m_0 v$ is an energy flux. This leads to a kind of modulus equation:

$$EE = ppcc + m_0 m_0 c c c c \quad ((4))$$

Link With Quantum Mechanics

We have argued above that p (momentum) can be measured without a clock through impulse hits. Given that a photon does not have a rest frame, this seems like the way to measure momentum for it and so this becomes a general approach. In other words, momentum seems to be linked to a scenario of no clock measurements. This immediately breaks with classical mechanics which follows a particle through $x(t)$.

We argued above that for a photon $x'/t'=c$ and also that $-Et+px = 0$. If p is associated with no clock measurements, then px should be a stand alone piece meaning that $pdxx=\text{constant}$ suggests a length $x = \text{constant}/p$. In turn one may create a kind of probability based on this, namely $\exp(ipx)$ such that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ and $\int \exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)dx=0$ if $p_1 \neq p_2$, i.e. conservation of momentum. Thus, it seems that the key ideas of quantum mechanics for a free particle may follow from the notion of no rest frame, i.e. a photon, and carry over to a particle with rest mass for consistency, at least for the spatial $\exp(ipx)$ part.

We note that in the case of time, a particle with rest mass and no p is still linked with a clock which ticks even though there is no motion through space. Thus, p is linked with no clock measurements and energy with a clock measurement. If one treats $-Et$ as a stand-alone piece, then $t=\text{constant}/E$ may represent a time period or time resolution.

Thus, we suggest that separation of t and x for measurements of E and p lead to the quantum idea of x resolution = \hbar/p and time resolution, \hbar/E .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider Maxwell's equations in the case of no charge sources or currents, as Maxwell did. Instead of obtaining explicit equations, we argue that such an approach means that there is no rest frame, but there are still energy and momentum values as well as densities as provided by electromagnetic theory. We argue that in order to have p , one must have motion, i.e. a speed. We argue, however, that this speed must be constant because otherwise one could arrange speeds from lowest to highest and the lowest would point to the closest thing to a rest frame. Nonrelativistically, KE has the units of $p \cdot \text{speed}$ so we suggest $E=|p|c$ or $EE = ppcc$ for the no rest frame scenario. For the no rest frame scenario, p is not $m_0 v$, and so is not measured using a clock, but rather through impulse hits. Thus, we suggest that to be consistent, one may consider that momentum is not measured using a clock.

$KE = p^2/2m_0$ nonrelativistically for a rest frame, but this differs completely from $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$ with E also being a kinetic energy. We suggest that the two should be of the same form. This implies that rest mass which exists in the rest frame must represent energy so that m_0 and $p=0$ may transform to E and p like E and p in $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$ transform. This suggests the form $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$ which is like a kind of modulus and handles p and $-p$. As a result, for $p=0$, one has energy linked with rest mass with a clock ticking while p is measured with no clock. The photon was responsible for the p with no clock measurement, but we suggest that rest mass which has a clock ticking is responsible for the notion of energy linked with time. We showed that $-Et + px = 0$ for the photon case. For the rest mass case $-Et + px = -m_0ct$ ($c=1$). For p linked with a no clock measurement and E with a clock present, we suggest that one has the beginnings of the ideas of quantum mechanics with a time resolution of \hbar/E and a spatial one of \hbar/p